

Direct determination of cobalt, chromium and manganese in gallium matrix by ETA-AAS technique

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An electrothermal atomization-atomic absorption spectrometric (ETA-AAS) method has been developed for the direct determination of Co, Cr and Mn in gallium matrix. The selective removal of volatile matrix has been achieved in the pre-atomization stage by controlling the furnace temperature at 1300° during the heating cycle. Nanogram amounts of analytes can be determined using 5 μ l of 10 mg/ml gallium sample aliquot with a precision of 8% R.S.D.

High purity gallium has important usage in electronic/semiconductor industry as also in the preparation of GaAs lasers. Since the electrical/optical properties of gallium are largely governed by its purity, the emphasis has been on preparation of materials with highest purity possible. Literature refers to semiquantitative determination of impurities in Ga by emission spectrography with direct current excitation of the sample in the metallic or oxide form¹ or by using electrothermal atomization-atomic absorption spectrometry (ETA-AAS) with prior separation and pre-concentration of impurities from the gallium matrix by solvent extraction². The ETA-AAS method being highly selective, a report based on use of matrix modifier in direct determination of Sn in Ga have appeared in the literature³. These reports elaborate the use of ascorbic acid, palladium nitrate etc. as matrix modifiers. The selection criteria for matrix modifiers according to their chemical nature for the ETA-AAS method have also appeared in the literature⁴.

As part of the program on development of analytical methodologies for direct determination of a host of trace metals in gallium which are detrimental to its rated performance, an ETA-AAS approach has been adopted for the direct determination of Co, Cr and Mn in gallium matrix. The present method envisages avoidance of lengthy chemical separation procedure but all the same, securing near total removal of major matrix without any loss of the analyte in the pre-atomization stage by optimizing sample heating program.

Results and discussion

Literature reports⁵ on the analysis of gallium/gallium arsenide refer to the prior separation of the matrix as either gallium trichloride/bromide by volatilization technique with ammonium chloride serving as matrix modifier. The present

work, however, is based on direct determination of trace metals in gallium matrix so as not to lose any of the volatile halides of analytes. In view of the applicability of ETA-AAS methods to analyze impurities directly in Ga samples, Ga concentration was required to be optimized. This also prompted a detailed study of the analyte behavior in the presence of gallium matrix. Effect of Ga matrix was studied for these analytes by varying Ga concentration in the range 0–20 mg/ml. The atomization of analytes in the presence of gallium matrix posed two problems, viz. non-specific absorbance caused due to formation of volatile molecular species and the other one of fumes generated during volatilization of the major matrix causing physical obstruction to the light-path. Both these factors result in high absorbance values not related to analyte absorbance signals. The present studies were, therefore, aimed at reducing significantly these problems. The non-specific absorbance signal could be evaluated by using the background correction facility of deuterium lamp continuum which, in the present case, could be successfully applied due to high sampling frequency associated with the lamp operation. The heating program was examined carefully by varying the temperature, ramp time (maximum ramp rate being 2000°/s) and hold time at every stage of the heating cycle. The initial three steps in the heating cycle belonged essentially to the desolvation stage. The fourth step parameters were varied systematically to ensure minimum evolution of fumes during atomization stage. The pre-atomization stage removal of matrix fumes could be achieved at 1300° with a ramp time of 0.5 s for 300–1300° rise in temperature and a hold time of 50 s. The fourth stage temperature versus absorbance data for the typical case of Cr, is tabulated for pure gallium matrix (10 mg/ml) in Table 1. The result reveals that the 'absorbance' value monitored for the analytical line of Cr without any Cr being present in

Table 1. Fourth step (pre-atomization step) in the heating program for pure gallium matrix

Pre-atomization temp., °C	Absorbance*	
	Monitoring at analytical line : 425.4 nm for Cr and atomization temp. of 2700°	
800	0.870	
900	0.730	
950	0.660	
1100	0.190	
1150	0.185	
1200	0.145	
1250	0.045	
1300	0.030	

*Without any Cr in the sample aliquot.

the sample aliquot goes on reducing as the fourth step temperature (pre-atomization stage) is increased from 800° onwards. The value for 'absorbance' gets leveled off to blank absorbance value as the evolution of fumes becomes negligible at 1300° temperature. Similar results were obtained when the analytical lines for other analyte elements were monitored for the 'absorbance' recorded due to evolution of fumes.

The heating program optimized for each of the three analytes is given in Table 2. It shows an additional step undertaken (step 6) in the heating programme used in case

The formation of Ga₂O, is aided further by the active carbon atoms from the graphite tube as

The role played by active carbon atoms is not very clear as presence of these active carbon sites in the pyrolytic graphite tubes is itself questioned by some⁷ and supported by others⁸. This controversy has been discussed in detail recently by Volynsky⁹. It is, however, clear from eqn. (2) that a lower oxide of gallium, viz. Ga₂O is formed in gaseous state on interaction of matrix in solid form with carbon. This is swept out in the pre-atomization stage and thus the matrix is partially removed during the hold time of 50 s at 1300° for all the analytes, thereby improving the analyte signal for Co, Cr and Mn. The pre-atomization stage removal of gallium, however, worked only upto 10 mg/ml matrix concentration, beyond which the overwhelming emanation of fumes could not be controlled efficiently during the atomization. It was also essential to ensure that the volatilization of the matrix did not accompany loss of analytes. A gallium sample was therefore specially prepared with intermediate range concentration of three analytes and analyzed using the optimized procedure. These results showed good agreement between the added contents and the analyte amounts determined. This way, one could confirm removal of matrix interference significantly without affecting the

Table 2. Heating parameters for the analytes in graphite furnace

Heating program steps	Co			Cr			Mn		
	Temp. °C	Time (s)		Temp. °C	Time (s)		Temp. °C	Time (s)	
		Ramp	Hold		Ramp	Hold		Ramp	Hold
1	80	10.0	5.0	70	10.0	6.0	80	10.0	5.0
2	120	10.0	10.0	120	12.0	5.0	120	10.0	10.0
3	300	2.0	2.0	300	3.0	2.0	300	2.0	2.0
4	1300	0.5	50	1300	0.5	50	1300	0.5	50
5	2500	0.7	1.0	2700	1.0	1.0	2450	1.0	1.0
6	2700	1.0	1.0	2800	1.0	0.5	–	–	–
7	20	14.0	5.0	20	14.0	5.0	20	14.0	5.0

of Co and Cr to ensure complete removal of residual analytes.

The fumes could be ascribed to formation of a volatile lower oxide, viz. Ga₂O, probably because of high temperature and inert atmosphere prevailing during the heating cycle. The literature report⁶ supports the same and the probable chemical reaction is

analyte signals for all the three elements. Aqueous (non-matrix containing) sample solutions of these analytes were also atomized to find losses at pre-atomization stage, if any. The signals were, however, found to be the same as those with gallium matrix even with a relatively high pre-atomization temperature. The effect due to the presence of residual gallium could, however, be seen during the studies carried out to determine temperatures for the signal appearance

(T_{app}). These temperatures are higher than those observed for non-matrix containing analyte solutions¹⁰. The release of analyte atoms from the residual gallium matrix within the graphite furnace, thus, appears to be a difficult process and possible only at higher temperatures. Such a trend is likewise manifested by the poor slope values for the calibration curves for all the three analytes in gallium matrix. The T_{app} values for all the analytes in the presence and absence of gallium matrix are shown in Table 3. The analytical data such as analytical range and the lowest limit of

the matrix was volatilized in pre-atomization stage, the accumulation of the matrix was in reality, insignificantly low and the atomizer could be used for many more atomization cycles for all the three analytes without any adverse effect on the analyte absorbances. The analytical range and lowest limit of quantitative determination (for all the three analytes) are shown in Table 3.

Spiked sample solutions were prepared for the three analyte elements following dissolution of gallium. Results

Table 3. Analytical data for determination of Co, Cr and Mn in gallium matrix

Element, wavelength nm	Characteristic Conc., ng/ml		T_{app} , °C		Range of analysis $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Lowest limit of quantitative determination $\times 10^{-11}$ (g)
	Aqu	Ga	Aqu*	Ga		
Co, 240.7	1.8	4.4	1430	1830	0.02–0.2	10.0
Cr, 425.4	1.8	2.2	1660	1950	0.01–0.2	5.0
Mn, 403.1	2.1	4.1	1480	1620	0.005–0.1	2.5

*Ref. 10.

quantitative determination are also shown in the table. Though the slopes of the analytical curves are poorer in the case of matrix containing standards due to poor atomization efficiency, the analytical range remained the same, thereby, making the analysis of the gallium samples feasible without prior chemical separation of the major matrix. Characteristic concentrations (concentration corresponding to an absorbance equal to 0.0044) for all analytes as obtained from calibration graphs, are given in Table 3 in presence and in absence of gallium matrix. In case of Co and Mn, the sensitivity as seen from characteristic concentration values is lower by a factor of two while it is marginally lower for Cr in the presence of Ga-matrix.

Effect of the presence of other common metallic elements, viz. Pb, Cu, Al, Fe, Mg, Ni, Zn, Sn, Ag, Ti and Si at concomitant levels on the absorbances of the three analytes were also studied. The absorbances for each of the three analytes were found to remain the same in presence and in absence of these other elements. Since the same atomizer was used repeatedly for successive analyses, the effect of residual matrix buildup in atomizer on analyte signal was studied. Absorbance signals were measured using 5 μl aliquot containing Co–0.1, Cr–0.1 and Mn–0.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with 10 mg/ml Ga-matrix. On repeated loading of the solution, the absorbance signal was found to remain unaffected for these analytes even upto 50-atomization cycles, equivalent to the addition of 2.5 mg Ga-matrix in the atomizer. As most of

of the analysis of these samples are shown in Table 4, with five replicate measurements, for each solution. The concentration of analytes determined in these samples are in good agreement with the spiked concentrations added to the gallium. Repetitive analysis of the three synthetic samples for each of the three analytes showed precision values in the range 6–8% RSD. In contrast to the chemical separation procedure generally adopted in such cases, the present method ensures least handling of the sample and also minimal contamination as against the one occurring due to extensive use of the chemical reagents during the matrix separation procedure. The method developed here, has found its applicability in ascertaining the chemical composition of

Table 4. Results of direct determination of Co, Cr and Mn in spiked gallium samples

Element	Concentration of spike				% R.S.D.
	Added		Measured		
	$\mu\text{g/ml}$	$\mu\text{g/g}$	$\mu\text{g/ml}$	$\mu\text{g/g}$	
Co	0.05	5.0	0.05	5.0	8
	0.1	10.0	0.11	10.5	7
	0.2	20.0	0.21	21.0	6
Cr	0.02	2.0	0.02	2.2	8
	0.05	5.0	0.05	5.0	8
	0.20	20.0	0.19	19.0	6
Mn	0.01	1.0	0.01	1.1	8
	0.05	5.0	0.05	5.2	8
	0.10	10.0	0.10	10.2	7

highly pure gallium samples used in the electronic industry.

Experimental

A GBC 906 atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS) with GF 3000-electrothermal atomizer of GBC (Australia) was used. A deuterium lamp was provided for the background correction with a sampling frequency of 200 Hz. All the measurements were carried out in peak height mode. The temperature-time and absorbance-time profiles for the absorbance were obtained for each atomization cycle. These were then used to investigate the atomization behavior.

High purity Supra pure (E. Merck) HCl and HNO₃, and double-distilled water were used. Stock solution of Ga (spec pure, Johnson Matthey) was prepared by dissolving an appropriate weighed amount of Ga metal in a platinum crucible using conc. nitric acid and the solution was evaporated to dryness and finally made to 20 mg/ml concentration in 0.1 M nitric acid. Stock solutions of Co, Cr and Mn (spec pure, Johnson Matthey, U.K.) were made by dissolving appropriate amounts of their compounds in 3 M nitric acid at 2 mg/ml concentration. Standard solutions were prepared by diluting stock solutions with double-distilled water. The acid concentration in all the diluted solutions was maintained at 0.1 M nitric acid.

Sets of single element standards with graded amounts of the analytes in the range 0.005–0.2 µg/ml were prepared without and with Ga-matrix (upto 20 mg/ml) to study the effect of presence of Ga on Co, Cr and Mn analyte absorbance. On optimization of Ga concentration at 10 mg/ml, a series of multi-element standards was prepared for these analytes with interfering elements, viz. Pb, Cu, Al, Fe, Mg, Ni, Zn, Sn, Ag, Ti and Si each at concomitant level. Three spiked samples were prepared with analyte concentrations covering the analytical range.

Procedure : A 5 µl aliquot of sample/standard solution was injected into graphite furnace and the six-step furnace heating cycle was followed. In order to remove memory effect for Co and Cr, an additional step for tube cleaning at

2700° and 2800°, respectively, were also introduced. In all the cases, the last step for bringing the system to ambient temperature was carried out.

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